

INDIA'S CORPORATE WORLD AND TRANSGENDER'S RIGHT TO EMPLOYMENT

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ABSTRACT

For many years, we have been talking about gender ceiling and women's right to equal salary, in this binary world it seems as if there is no existence of the third gender i.e., transgender community. Transgender people are human beings just like us they just have their own tastes, preferences, styles etc. Nevertheless, their preferences don't make them less human and not worthy of employment. It is quite strange to observe that people who were venerated in India's ancient times are denied even basic rights in the modern era. Almost 90% of transgender people are not able to participate in any economic activity. But unfortunately, there are very few government policies working on inclusion of trans community so here in this paper we have discussed how Indian corporate companies through their efforts can contemplate and even lead the way in providing equal employment opportunities to transgenders which they have been deserving since decades.

INTRODUCTION

The official definition of transgender is-

“of, relating to, or being a person whose gender identity differs from the sex the person had or was identified as having at birth especially : of, relating to, or being a person whose gender identity is opposite the sex the person had or was identified as having at birth”¹.

In simple terms it means any person whose gender identity is different from their birth sex. For example, a person was born as male, but his nature was feminine and he used to wear women's clothes, do makeup like a woman, etc. Then that person is known as transgender. It has many terms associated with it like trans, trans male/female, third gender, etc. However, many a times people get confused between the term transgender and sexual orientation. Transgender is a type of gender whereas sexual orientation is about romantic or sexual preferences. So, a transgender can have their own sexual orientation like gay, lesbian, straight etc. As transgender people do not conform to ‘normal’ standards of society, they are one of the most discriminated (high risk group). Historically speaking, they were banished from society, started living in the outskirts and formed their own colonies. In some countries they were even tortured and murdered. Due to their non acceptance in society, they were denied many rights including basic ones. They faced many issues like gender inclusive public toilets, lack of education, poverty, denial of jobs etc. But things have changed now. Today, transgender people are given the status of equal human beings by the virtue of Article 14 in Indian Constitution. However, they are still discriminated against when it comes to the workplace. According to 2018 survey, nearly 96% of transgender people are denied jobs even if they are qualified and are forced to take low paying jobs or even take disrespectful work like sex workers, begging².

IN INDIAN CULTURE

¹ MERRIAM WEBSTER, <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/transgender> (last visited Mar. 22,2022).

² MONEY CONTROL, <https://www.moneycontrol.com/news/india/about-96-of-transgenders-are-denied-jobs-60-have-never-attended-schools-study-2836281.html> (last visited Mar. 22,2022).

Transgender people existed all over the world since ancient times. They were represented in cultures of various countries and even in mythologies. However, only a few cultures recognised the significance of their existence. One such culture was Indian culture. Recognition of transgender people can be found in the scriptures of Jainism, Hinduism and Buddhism. According to Hinduism, the concept of transgender was known as “tritiyaprakriti” or “napumsaka”. Also, these people were mentioned in mythology as well. In Ramayana, when Lord Ram was sentenced to 14 years of vanvas, it was the transgender people who stood with him while other men and women were asked to return to the city. So Lord Ram conferred them powers to bless newborns, married couples etc. Even in Mahabharata, Lord Krishna (by being a beautiful woman ‘Mohini’) married Aravan who is considered as progenitor of Tamil Transgenders³. Transgender people were even venerated during the reign of Mughals. They hold high positions (like administrators, advisors, etc.) because of their trustworthiness and loyalty. However, the era of British regime marked the beginning of discrimination of transgender people (Hijra community). They were denied civil rights and were later criminalised through Criminal Tribes Act, 1871 which was later repealed in 1952. By the time the act was repealed, Hijra people were considered to be a separate caste in many parts of India. So the blessing given by Lord Ram turned out to be bane as today transgenders are limited to these roles of merely a person who blesses families and take begging.

CURRENT CRISIS

How many year has it been since we have talked about women’s right to equal wages and glass ceiling but why have we never talked about transgender’s right to employment. Since the very childhood transgender people are not given equal education opportunities, according to the survey conducted by NHRC in 2017 in which 900 transgender people from four districts of UP and NCR were surveyed “three in four transgender persons in NCR and 82% in Uttar Pradesh were never in school or dropped out before grade X.” Transgender people generally drop out of school because of severe harassment and gender related negative experience they face in school.

Due to this lack of education opportunities they are generally employed in low paid and informal sector job and in worst cases as sex workers. According to the same NHRC survey “Nearly 15% had no jobs and 69% were working in the informal sector, primarily engaged in singing, dancing and 'blessing' [Transgender persons from some communities are invited to give blessings at weddings or after child birth. For many people, this is a significant source of income]. Three in four respondents were dissatisfied with their career or income generating

³ M. Michelraj, *Historical Evolution of Transgender Community in India*, 4 ARSS 17, 2 2015, [ARSS-Vol.4-No.1-Jan-June-2015-pp.17-19.pdf \(trp.org.in\)](https://www.arss.org.in/ARSS-Vol.4-No.1-Jan-June-2015-pp.17-19.pdf).

activities and 53% were earning less than Rs 10,000 per month.” And according to another survey by “Sangama, a human rights organisation interviewed 3,619 transgender persons--found that only 12% of the transgender persons surveyed were employed and half of the respondents made less than Rs 5,000 per month”.⁴

So as you can see there is strong need to make acts protecting and encouraging equal rights of transgender community.

LEGAL PROVISIONS

After the criminalisation of transgenders through the Criminal Tribes Act, 1871; many workplace related laws followed the suit. Acts like Workmen’s Compensation Act, 1923, Payment of Gratuity Act, 1972, Factories Act, 1968, etc. systematically excluded transgender people from equal protection at the workplace. These acts conformed to gender binary and blatantly ignored the ‘third gender’⁵. These repressive laws denied them the right to get compensation in case of accidents as dependents included only male and female. At present many laws need to be amended to protect transgender people at the workplace. For instance, Equal Remuneration Act, 1976 prohibits wage - based discrimination between a man and woman at the workplace which is gender binary and excludes transgender to claim equal wage pay. Similarly Maternity Benefit Act, 1961 provides maternal benefits only to women and excludes trans women. After passing certain landmark judgements like NALSA v. Union of India⁶ and refocusing on laws like Article 14, 16, 17 etc, the Government of India has made certain attempts to fix this discrimination. Some of these attempts are as follows: -

The Transgender Persons (Protection of Rights) Bill, 2016 - It was introduced in the Lok Sabha in August 2016. It seeks to prohibit discrimination of transgender on the matters of education, workplace, healthcare, property rights, etc.⁷ It applies to both public and private places and protects them from discrimination in the workplace in all matters like hiring, increments, promotions etc. It also provided for the establishment of National Council for Transgenders (NCT) which will be comprised of ministers, transgender’s people, government organisations etc. who will help in drafting policies for the welfare of transgender people. It also proposed actions against those who violate the rules. However, this bill was filled with many flaws. These flaws included unclear definition of the transgender person, unclear terms in the definition, differences in definitions of other international bodies etc. The bill also missed out reservation of transgender people and punishment for the offences like rape, molestation,

⁴ IndiaSpend, <https://www.indiaspend.com/gendercheck/denied-visibility-in-official-data-millions-of-transgender-indians-cant-access-benefits-services-754436> (last visited Mar. 22,2022).

⁵ VIDHI LEGAL POLICY, [Queering-the-Law Employment.pdf](https://www.vidhilegalpolicy.in/queering-the-law-employment.pdf) (vidhilegalpolicy.in) (last visited Apr.1, 2022).

⁶ NALSA V. Union of India, AIR 2014 SC 1863.

⁷ PRS INDIA, [The Transgender Persons \(Protection of Rights\) Bill, 2016](https://prsindia.org/bills-and-legislation/the-transgender-persons-protection-of-rights-bill-2016) (prsindia.org) (last visited Apr.1, 2022).

sexual harassment etc. against them. So, the bill was received with much criticism and it didn't satisfy the transgender community even after 27 amendments.

Transgender Persons (Protection of Rights) Bill, 2019 - It was passed in order to make the country more inclusive to the transgender people. It mainly had the same features as the previous bills. It included setting up NCT, certificate of identity, prohibition of discrimination in workplace related matters. This time it applied the definition which is fit as per international standards. However, it also lacked some essential measures like reservation of transgender people in jobs, stringent punishment for offences like rape & sexual harassment, self-identification (lack of it leads to violation of Article 21), etc.

Transgender Persons (Protection of Rights) Bill, 2020 - It came in order to justify the 2019 Bill. It was introduced in the lockdown period and thus no discussions were done with the stakeholders, especially the trans community. It has similar features like that of the 2019 Bill with some minor procedural changes. As a result, it was faced with heavy criticism by transgender people and the intellectuals. It still had the lighter punishment for heinous crimes like sexual abuse against the transgender which violated Section 375 of the IPC as punishment prescribed for the crime is 2 years instead of 7 years mentioned. Also, no such due importance was given to self-identification.

So, it can be said that existing legal provisions for the protection of transgender people in the workplace is not satisfactory. Many amendments with stringent punishment and clear terms need to take place in order to safeguard our trans people.

INDIAN COMPANIES BRINGING CHANGE

Today many companies worldwide are looking at LGBTQ inclusion not just from a humanitarian perspective but also as a decision that makes business sense. According to report prepared by the World bank on marginalisation and loss in GDP-

“India's loss in GDP due to homophobia and transphobia up to \$32 billion, or 1.7% of our GDP”

Apart from capital, today's market is intensely engaged in the 'war for talent' and if companies don't update on their diversity policy, then they will face the risk of losing talent. Global companies like Apple, H&M, Dell, Goldman Sachs, Google, IBM, Accenture etc. are changing policies and making their workplace more inclusive. Hence Indian companies, especially IT who want to compete on a global level, need to welcome employees from diverse backgrounds and be mindful of their needs. Companies need to understand today's millennials and Gen

Y want to be part of something bigger even while shopping for clothes or tea. So companies are being LGBTQ inclusive even in their ad campaigns like “Vicks Touch of Care campaign was centred around trans motherhood and featured trans rights activist Gauri Sawant”. A company can gain increased press coverage by changing policies and becoming inclusive like Vicks above campaign helped it to increase its sales. And moreover companies committed to diversity are more likely to respond to the changing needs of their customers and clients hence companies can utilise the insights of their LGBTQ employees to understand LGBTQ market.

So, we try to bring forward some Indian companies bringing change in the culture especially for transgenders-

TATA Steel- The Tata company had decided that by 2021 they will have at least 5% LGBTQ employees and they began this from their roots itself. The company firstly made sure that all employees understood what was expected of them and were on board with the initiative through gender sensitization training. The company created Employee Resource Group for LGBT population, workplace integration modules which can be deployed anytime for other employees when someone comes out as trans, with a special focus on training HRs to handle situations appropriately. The company is taking measures such as providing special leave for employees who undergo gender affirmation surgery, as well as financial support, relocation to a different city for better social and medical support on request, and gender-neutral washrooms.

Lalit hotels - “Lalit Suri Hospitality Group” shines out in the service sector because of their dedication towards the “UN Business Standards of Conduct.” All employees in the company go through a sensitization program not only for LGBT but also for victims of acid attack. The company’s efforts in creating an inclusive atmosphere are commendable in every document of company gender a non-mandatory detail and third gender is given as option, gender neutral washrooms are made, gender neutral communication is used and strict anti-discrimination policy is applied throughout the organization. The organisation has hired 35 trans employees so far and even placed them in positions of visibility in their establishments. The company has even tied up with ICICI Lombard to get Mediclaim policies for partners and children of its LGBTQ employees.

Godrej- “Nisaba Godrej, director, Godrej Consumer Products Ltd (GCPL)” was asked when the company since last 120 years had strictly followed no discrimination policy then why just on the basis of caste, gender, religion and not sexuality. This five - minute conversation with her and Parmesh Sahani made the company LGBT inclusive back in the year 2010 itself. The company changed its HR policies like allowing employees to choose third gender, making infrastructure like gender neutral washrooms, changing the term spouse to partner in policies

and extending benefits to them, giving LGBTQ individuals three month break for primary care giving if they choose to adopt, allowing same sex partners in committed relationship to access benefits like treatment at group's hospital and even reimbursing health insurance. The company organised a dancing queen event with transgenders to remove the fear and prejudices related to Hijra community in employees and many employees like Kevin Lobo admit how these gender sensitisation events removed all the wrong assumptions about LGBTQ community in their mind.⁸

VLCC- One of the major problems faced in hiring transgenders is lack of skills and to solve this in 2018 the company trained around twenty-five transgenders as beauty therapists. They were prepared to work for various positions in VLCC and other beauty and health-related institutions. A stipend of Rs. 2000 was also granted to them. The Humsafar Trust and VLCC Institute collaborated on this training. A workshop on gender sensitisation was hosted at the SR Nagar for VLCC employees to create an inclusive workplace for their future trans employees.

Infosys- This tech giant has zero tolerance discrimination policy and fosters a culture of equality where “people—regardless of their gender identity or sexual orientation—can bring their authentic selves to work”. It has formed an Employee Resource Group (ERG) for LGBT to make sure that by connecting themselves, they create a dialogue and present the problems faced by them regarding the company's policies. The company also held gender sensitization workshops to create safe and harassment free workplaces. The company plans to change its HR policies and infrastructure in the near future and make it more inclusive.⁹

Tech Mahindra- The company has created LGBT community groups called kaleidoscopes across the different parts of the country to create cultural assimilation and sensitise people. The company also provides 12 weeks paid adoption leave to same sex couple and even now allowing them to work from home in the first year of parenthood. It is also in process of adding a gamification element to its diversity and inclusion training and creating an immersive experience for all its employees.¹⁰

⁸ DNA INDIA, <https://www.dnaindia.com/lifestyle/report-it-is-all-about-inclusion-at-godrej-2239553> (last visited Mar. 22,2022).

⁹ TIMES OF INDIA, <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/city/pune/when-it-stands-for-inclusion/articleshow/59753027.cms> (last visited Mar. 22,2022).

¹⁰ ECONOMIC TIMES, https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/tech/ites/tech-mahindra-introduces-new-policies-for-lgbtq-employees/articleshow/72979136.cms?utm_source=contentofinterest&utm_medium=text&utm_campaign=cppst (last visited Mar. 22,2022).

CONCLUSION

With the help of various theories and philosophies, it is been proved that transgender people are not someone inhuman or abnormal. They are very much like us and they deserve to live life with as much dignity as a normal human beings live. However, there are many instances where such people are denied basic human rights which includes being denied or fired from jobs. Even though the government has taken steps to prohibit this discrimination, such unjustified practices are still followed in many workplaces. Giving transgenders some jobs as per their capabilities has a positive impact in the society and workplace both. Other companies should follow practices of companies like TATA, Godrej, Lalit hotels etc. in order to include the trans community into the corporate world and being an inspiration to help other transgender people to come out of the dark web of discrimination and live like a normal dignified human being. Government doesn't put much efforts to reach out to transgender people. There are many government schemes which can be used by transgenders but only one scheme (Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Grameen Kaushalya Yojana) includes trans people as one of the beneficiaries. It's high time for the government to take certain measures to uplift their lives through the way of reservation, progressive laws, stringent punishment etc.

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